

Identifying and Isolating of *H. pylori* in patients who are experiencing Inflammation in their Gastrointestinal tract

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 09 January 2024	Background: Peptic ulcer illness, stomach cancer and chronic gastritis are gastro-duodenal diseases that are mostly caused by <i>Helicobacter pylori</i> , or <i>H. pylori</i> . Objective: To find out how common <i>Helicobacter pylori</i> infection is among patients at Al Sadder Teaching Hospital in Al-Najaf, Iraq, as well as related factors including age, gender, residency, and blood group. Methods: The entirety of 197 patients—79 men and 118 women—of both genders and various age groups—from under 10 to around 60 years old—were reported to have symptoms of gastrointestinal inflammation. Result: The total numbers of participants in the current study were 197 patients, found 156 (79.2%) positive and 41 (20.8%) negative results. Females had a greatest percentage of <i>H. pylori</i> (47.2%), while males had the lowest incidence of prevalence (32%). The age group (31-40) had greatest percentage with (14.7%), followed by the age group (41-50) with (13.2%), and then the age group (21-30) with (11.7%) while lowest percentages in age groups < 10 and > 60 years old. The blood group type O, which had the greatest positive rate (27.9%), was followed by the blood groups types A, B, and AB, with 16.8%, 13.7%, and 4.1%, respectively. People who live in rural areas (30.4%) have a elevated frequency of <i>H. pylori</i> infection when compared with persons who reside in urban areas (28.4%). Conclusion: The findings showed that <i>H. pylori</i> was more frequent in women than men, in rural areas, and in patients between the ages of 31 and 40. Additionally, individuals with the O blood group had higher <i>H. pylori</i> frequency.
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INTRODUCTION:

Originally known as *Campylobacter pylori*, "*Helicobacter pylori*" is spiral-shaped, genus *Helicobacteraceae*, gram-ve, microaerophilic, motile bacillus that moves into the stomach and passes through the mucous gastric layer (bind to blood group antigens that are expressed on the stomach mucosa's surface) or superior part of small intestine and is most frequently observed in the duodenum's gastric metaplasia sites and the stomach antrum (can thrive in the stomach's extremely acidic environment). Because it does not pass through the epithelial barrier. *Helicobacter pylori* is considered non-invasive and is linked to chronic gastritis, peptic ulcers, duodenal ulcers, and gastritis. Additionally, it has been linked to the developing stomach adenocarcinoma and mucosa associated lymphoid tissue lymphoma (MALT) (Hussain et al., 2008 ; Ansari and Yamaoka , 2017).

Multifactorial etiology is thought to explain the pathophysiology of *Helicobacter pylori*. Environmental variables, host genotypes, immunological response, and bacterial virulence factors are considered to be involved in this microorganism's pathogenesis. Numerous studies have connected *H. pylori* to a range of disorders outside of the stomach. These include migraine, thrombocytopenic purpura, Guillain-Barre syndrome, ischemic heart disease, scleroderma, autoimmune thyroiditis, Raynaud's phenomenon and skin conditions such idiopathic urticaria and thrombocytopenic purpura (Gravina et al., 2018).

This bacteria's release of biochemical's and ammonia generation such phospholipases, urease, proteases, and vacuolating cytotoxin A which greatly increase the bacterium's susceptibility for inflammation and cancer. (Dhakal and Dhakal, 2018). Though its exact mode of

transmission *Helicobacter pylori* is unknown, drinking water polluted with feces has suggested a potential cause of infectivity. *H. pylori* can also spread orally or through the faecal-oral route (Klein et al., 1991; Mladenova et al., 2006).

There are no specific clinical signs and symptoms associated with *H. pylori*, and most patients are asymptomatic. On the other hand, nausea, vomiting, heartburn, esophagitis, diarrhea, delayed stomach emptying, evening starvation, and foul breath are typical indications and symptoms (Ayodele et al., 2018).

The majority of developing nations, including Iraq, have very dispersed epidemiological data regarding the incidence of infection with *H. pylori*, the incidence of infection with *H. pylori* was roughly 55.8% in Erbil (Hussen et al., 2013), in Basrah city with 54.5% (Amer et al., 2014), in Baghdad city with 59.2% (Al-Mossawei et al., 2016), in Hilla city with 51.1% (Al-Sabary et al., 2017), in Tikrit city with 55.8% (Alsamarai et al., 2017), in Sulaimani city about 51.2% (Mohammed et al., 2017), in Kirkuk city approximately 49.62% (Abdul Razaq et al., 2017), in Misan city about 51.11% (Alhashimi et al., 2017), in Mosul city with 61.32% (Ali, 2018), and finally in Duhok city with 28% (Yahya, 2018) was found.

In developing nations, *H. pylori* is present in approximately 70%–90% of the general population, with most infections occurring during childhood; in industrialized nations, the incidence ranges from 30% to 40%. This higher percent due to many reasons that assist with this infection such social circumstances, age, economic status, low levels of education, poor nutrition, living in an urban area, overcrowding, insufficient hygiene, running water, ethnicity, geographical distribution, gender, a poor water supply, and fast food intake (Bello et al., 2018).

Both invasive and noninvasive techniques exist to diagnosing *H. pylori* infectivity. The invasive technique uses polymerase chain reaction, histological testing, culture, endoscopy, rapid urease test and biopsy. The stool antigen test, serological testing, urinary antibody test and the urea breath test are

examples of non-invasive techniques (Majeed and Abdullah, 2019). Immunochromatographic testing is one of the serological methods that is frequently employed to diagnose *H. pylori* due to low cost and easy availability at any laboratories (Rishma et al., 2018).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

1-Sampling

Cross-sectional study was done at the Al Sadder Teaching Hospital in Al-Najaf, Iraq, during the period September to October 2023. Prior to their enrollment in the clinical study, each individual participant provided written consent. 197 patients (79 men and 118 women) of both sexes and varying age groups—from under 10 to around 60 years old—were reported to have symptoms of gastrointestinal inflammation (digestive dysmotility, nausea and vomiting disorders, duodenal inflammation, stomach inflammation, reflux, epigastric discomfort and burning). The patient personal information, such as age, gender, and residence location (urban & rural). These specimens were performed for bacteriological analysis at Microbiology department/ faculty of Medicine/ Jabir Ibn Hayyan University for medical and pharmaceutical sciences.

2- *H. pylori* Ab detection in plasma or serum samples of blood.

The process of directly diagnosing *Helicobacter pylori* infection by serum antibody detection was carried out by Wondfo, One Step *H. Pylori* Serum/Plasma Test (Guangzhou Wondfo Biotech Co., Ltd. China) is a quick chromatographic immunoassay that helps diagnose *H. pylori* infection by qualitatively detecting antibodies to *H. pylori* bacteria in serum or plasma. The test protocol was followed in accordance with the test booklet provided by:

- 1- One drop of whole blood serum or plasma should be dispensed into the cassette's well. As shown in Fig. 1.
- 2- After adding the specimen, add two drops of sample diluents (buffer) to sample pad's lower edge.
- 3- Examine results later than 15 minutes

Fig 1: Wondfo, One Step H.Pylori Serum/Plasma Test

3- Monoclonal Blood Grouping Reagents (Lorne Laboratories Limited, UK)

Red blood cells with the ABO antigen will directly clump together due to the presence of antibodies against the antigen on human red blood cells in these reagents. The absence of ABO antigen on human red blood cells is often shown by the absence of agglutination.

RESULTS

The total numbers of participants in the current study were 197 patients, found 156 (79.2%) positive and 41(20.8%) negative results. Fig 2

Fig 2: Positive H.Pylori Serum/Plasma Test

Table 1 displays the frequencies of *H. pylori* detection by gender. The high positive percentage was 93 (47.2%) in females and the low positive percentage was 63 (32%) in males.

Table 1: H. pylori prevalence according gender.

Genders	H. pylori Test		Total
	+ve (%)	-ve(%)	
Male	63 (32%)	16 (8.1%)	79 (40.1%)
Female	93 (47.2%)	25 (12.7%)	118 (59.9%)
Total	156 (79.2%)	41 (20.8%)	197 (100%)

The age group (31-40) had the greatest percentage of *Helicobacter pylori* infection, with 29 (14.7%), followed by the age group (41-50) with 26 (13.2%), and the age group (21-30) with 23 (11.7%). The age groups < 10 and > 60 years old

had the lowest percentages of *Helicobacter pylori* infection, with 0.5% and 1.0%, respectively. According to Table 2.

Table 2: Age-related *H. pylori* infections

Age	No.	H. pylori Test	
		+ve (%)	-ve (%)
<10	1(0.5%)	1(0.5%)	0(0%)
11-20	12(6.1%)	8(4.1%)	4(2%)
21-30	67 (34%)	23(11.7%)	44(22.3%)
31-40	50 (25.4%)	29(14.7%)	21(10.7%)
41-50	44(22.4 %)	26(13.2%)	18(9.2%)
51-60	18(9.1 %)	12(6.1%)	6(3%)
>60	5(2.5 %)	2(1.0%)	3(1.5%)
Total	197 (100%)	101(51.3%)	96(48.7%)

The blood group type O, which had the greatest positive rate (27.9%), was followed by the blood groups types A, B, and

AB, with 16.8%, 13.7%, and 4.1%, respectively. According to Table 3's illustration.

Table 3: Distribution of anti-H. pylori antibodies by blood group.

Blood group	H. pylori Test		Total
	+ve (%)	-ve(%)	
A	33 (16.8%)	20 (10.1%)	53 (26.9%)
B	27 (13.7%)	14 (7.1%)	41 (20.8%)
AB	8 (4.1%)	17 (8.6%)	25 (12.7%)
O	55(27.9%)	23(11.7%)	78 (39.6%)
Total	123 (62.5)	74 (37.6)	197 (100%)

The frequency of *H. pylori* infection was found to vary by residential region, with urban regions reporting an elevated

prevalence of 56 (28.4%) and rural regions reporting a low prevalence of 60 (30.4%). Based on Table 4.

Table 4: Infection with *Helicobacter pylori* accordance to residency.

Residency	H. pylori Test		Total
	+ve (%)	-ve (%)	
Rural	60 (30.4%)	47 (23.9%)	107 (54.3%)
Urban	56 (28.4%)	34 (17.3%)	90 (45.7%)
Total	116 (58.8%)	81(41.2%)	197 (100%)

DISCUSSION

Helicobacter pylori is a serious global health concern that is essential to the pathophysiology of stomach cancer, which is the 5th most frequent type of cancer and the 3rd largest cause of mortality globally (Asghar and Parsonnet, 2001).

The current study finds that 79.2% of people had *H. pylori* infection. This is analogous to previous studies where reports of *H. pylori* infection have been made, such as those from Baghdad, Iraq (71.3%) and Mosul, Iraq (61.32%) (Gutef, 2016; Ali, 2018). However, these results was inconsistent with studies by ALmashhadany (2018), who discovered a lower incidence of *H. pylori* infection in Erbil, Iraq, at 11.3%, and Yahya (2018), who discovered a lower frequency of *H. pylori* infection in Duhok, Iraq, at 28%. The patient's age and health, inadequate hygiene habits, the number of specimens, inappropriate eating habits, the cultural traditions of the population, the geographic distribution, high levels of

population density, ethnic background, testing procedures, and status in society could all of them explain the reason for this differences (Tsongo et al., 2015).

Females had a greatest percentage of *H. pylori* (47.2%), while males had the lowest incidence of prevalence (32%). The results we obtained were consistent with Yucelet al. (2008) in Turkey, who discovered that women were more susceptible to *H. pylori* infection, and Zhu et al. (2014), who discovered that women in China had a greater incidence of *H. pylori* infection than men. This finding, however, disagreements with that of Almashadany (2018), who discovered that men had an elevated prevalence of *H. pylori*. The difference in hormones between the sexes and the fact that women are more likely than men to take care of food preparation and spending a longer period in the kitchen and housekeeping may be the cause of the greater infection rate among the women in our study (Mohammed et al., 2017).

In context of age-specific frequency of *H. pylori*, the age group (31-40) had greatest percentage with (14.7%), followed by the age group (41-50) with (13.2%), and then the age group (21-30) with (11.7%) while lowest percentages in age groups < 10 and > 60 years old. This is consistent with findings published by Udoh and Obaseki (2012), who discovered that individuals with *H. pylori* have a greater rate of infectivity in the adult or younger age group. As though This contradicts a study published in 2016 by Gutef, which showed a significant incidence of *H. pylori* infection in people over 50. The elevated prevalence of *H. pylori* infection in adults as a result of risk factor exposure, the dietary habits of the patient, social and economic status, insufficient hygiene, water supply, unsanitary surroundings, and contaminated food and water (Al-Mossawei et al., 2016).

Blood group O had the highest positive rate (27.9%) when compared to other blood types, while the AB blood group was less likely to become infected. According to a different study conducted in Egypt, blood group O was positively correlated with *H. pylori* infection, suggesting that this consider a risk factor for *H. pylori* infection (Shaldoum, 2015). The same outcome reported by Jaff (2011), who determined that those with the O blood type have a higher cellular and immune response to *H. pylori* infection and are more vulnerable to infection.

According to our research, people who live in rural areas (30.4%) found a elevated frequency of *H. pylori* infection when compared with persons who reside in urban areas (28.4%). This is consistent with research conducted in Misan-Iraq (Alhashimi et al., 2017) but disagreement with the research carried out in Tanzania. These differences between patients in rural and urban regions could be caused by poor sewage disposal, poor water supplies, poor sanitation, population social habits, low levels of education, and ignorance of health issues (Jaka et al., 2016).

CONCLUSION

The findings showed that *H. pylori* was more frequent in women than men, in rural areas, and in patients between the ages of 31 and 40. Additionally, individuals with the O blood group had higher *H. pylori* frequency.

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